

Social Connectedness among University Students: A Science Mapping Review

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Among university students, loneliness is emerging as a very serious public health concern. It is found that social disconnection is directly related to mental and physical health risks. Social connectedness is defined as an individual's sense of belonging and perceived closeness to others. It plays a very important role in academic engagement, psychological well-being, and persistence in university courses. Research is increasing in this field, but the literature on social connectedness in university contexts still remains fragmented. To address this gap, this study uses a bibliometric approach to understand the recent research trends in the field. Data was collected from Scopus, which included the studies from 2018-2025. Bibliographic coupling was done to understand the recent trends in the area of social connectedness among university students. It revealed four major themes: "Situating Social Connectedness in STEM and Marginalized Contexts"; "Conceptualizing, Measuring, and Cultivating Social Connectedness"; "Social Connectedness as a Pathway to Well-Being, Engagement, and Persistence"; and "Social Connectedness as a Political, Relational, and Plural Experience". It is found that social connectedness is a dynamic, multidimensional, and contextually embedded concept. It is shaped by individual, relational, and structural factors. This study will be useful for researchers, policymakers, and institutions to enhance social connectedness among university students.

Keywords: Social connectedness, bibliometric analysis, university students

Loneliness is emerging as a global concern affecting the majority of people around the globe (WHO, 2025). It has been found that loneliness and long-term social isolation have a negative impact on mental as well as physical health, increasing the risk of depression, anxiety, cardiovascular problems, and even early mortality (Holt-Lunstad et al., 2015; Murthy, 2023). Social connectedness is at the opposite end of the spectrum to loneliness. It is defined as a fundamental human need to belong and to be part of the community (Baumeister & Leary 1995). It is a feeling of closeness to others (Lee & Robbins, 1998). As loneliness is increasing at a tremendous rate, global reports now consider social connection as a basic human need, equal to nutrition and exercise, and identify loneliness as a significant health risk (World Health Organisation [WHO], 2025). Despite this awareness, loneliness continues to rise, especially among the young population.

Young adulthood is that stage of life which can be particularly challenging in terms of social connections. Because during this time, individuals generally experience major transitions, like moving away from home to start higher education or work, and form new social networks (Munsey, 2006). Social connectedness supports emotional well-being, life satisfaction, and helps in coping with stress. Lack of social connectedness among young adults results in

the experience of psychological distress and declining mental health (WHO, 2025).

Among the young adult population, university students constitute a specific group of individuals. These students are especially vulnerable to loneliness as they have to compete in academics and at the same time, they have to build new relationships in a new environment with new people. Students who feel a sense of belongingness and connectedness at their universities, experience better mental health, greater resilience, and higher academic engagement (Slaten et al., 2016). Being socially integrated into the university is very important for student retention and well-being. Feeling socially and academically connected results in students persistence in their studies (Tinto, 1975). Students with high social connectedness are better able to cope with challenges, and those who lack social connectedness are more likely to experience stress, poor health, and even drop out of studies as well (Urke et al., 2023). They are at a greater risk of stress, loneliness, and academic disengagement (Cacioppo & Hawkley, 2003).

There are many changes happening in the university settings. Students coming from different backgrounds and places are enrolling in universities, resulting in a diverse student population. The number of international students enrolling in universities is increasing. Technological advancements like digital or hybrid learning, result in an additional challenge for students to form social connections (UNESCO Institute for Statistics et al., 2022). These changes can make it difficult for students to feel included and supported, especially for those who come from marginalized backgrounds (Su Ju, 2021).

Among university students, research on loneliness, and social connectedness is increasing, but remains scattered. There are only a few studies that have systematically examined trends in this area (Slaten et al., 2016). They have limitations, taking research only from a psychology background and only from a specific journal

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Social connectedness is very important if there is any kind of disruption or marginalization. A study during COVID-19 found that identifying with the university helped students in reducing isolation and enhancing motivation (Andreadis & Marshall, 2023). A longitudinal study proves that social connectedness reduces anxiety and depressive symptoms, especially for underrepresented and first-generation students (Gopalan et al., 2021). In STEM disciplines, it is found that competitive culture, hostile climate, and underrepresentation of certain groups can result in weak social connectedness that increases stereotype threat and disengagement (Derricks & Sekaquaptewa, 2021; Ladewig et al., 2020). If a student affirms seeing oneself as a “science person,” then it helps in strengthening the connectedness, which ultimately leads to better academic performance (Chen et al., 2020). It is also found that classroom practices, structured courses, peer networks, mentoring, and recognition programs help in improving social connectedness and persistence of students in courses (Clements et al., 2023; Bahnson et al., 2025). Being more than one identity and socio-economic factors also have an influence on social connectedness like socioeconomic status, first-generation background, minority status, and cultural mismatch, influences that how a student experiences social connectedness and well-being (Du et al., 2023; Fernandez et al., 2025; Google et al., 2023). International students face impostor feelings, mentoring gaps, language, and acculturation that result in low social connectedness (Preuß et al., 2025; Reid et al., 2019). But it is also found that social connectedness also develops over time (Stachl & Baranger, 2020).

Overall, Cluster 1 understands social connectedness as it is context dependent and unequal, but it is important for equity, persistence, and well-being in higher education.

Cluster 2: Conceptualizing, Measuring and Cultivating Social Connectedness

Cluster 2 represented by green color consists of 30 studies. It shifts the focus from situated risk to the conceptual, methodological and practical foundations of social connectedness research among university students. Social connectedness is not a single outcome but is multidimensional, dynamic, and influenced by academic, social, spatial, digital, and institutional contexts. Social connectedness among university students is the feeling of connectedness with learning, peers, relationships with physical spaces, cultural identity, life satisfaction, and personal interests, emphasising its situational yet personal nature (Ahn & Davis, 2019). Quantitative studies done among students have found that academic and social engagement predict social connectedness and retention (Ahn & Davis, 2020).

A systematic review defined social connectedness as feeling valued, safe, accepted, and included. It also mentions the barriers to social connectedness like feelings of exclusion, weak relationships, and little institutional support (Allen et al., 2024). It is found that in STEM and other professional programs, social connectedness is affected by competence, recognition, identity development, and persistence. Active learning, peer communities, and access to disciplinary social capital enhance social connectedness, whereas perceived incompetence and stereotype vulnerability reduce social connectedness (Bøe et al., 2024; Gray et al., 2025).

Different types of practices used by institutions also influence social connectedness. If teachers include an inclusive approach in their teachings and encourage co-curricular support among students,

then it can lead to enhanced social connectedness among students. In contrast, if the institutional norms marginalize students, it can be a threat to social connectedness (Harry et al., 2024; Malm et al., 2020). It is found that online platforms can function as facilitators as well as barriers to social connectedness. If collaborative activities are practiced, then they can enhance safety and social connectedness (Brodie & Osowska, 2021; Edwards & Hardie, 2024; Altes et al., 2023; Møgelvang et al., 2023). But if students feel that they are less visible on digital platforms, it can result in inequality and reduced social connectedness (Smith & Watson, 2022).

Intervention research has found that arts-based approaches, co-creative programs, structured STEM interventions, and help-seeking initiatives are found to strengthen the social connectedness and well-being among university students (Henrickson et al., 2024; Shortlidge et al., 2024; Sithaldeen et al., 2025), but some programs increase interaction without improving subjective connectedness (van Herpen et al., 2019).

Low levels of help coming from academic staff also result in diminished social connectedness (Stratton-Maher et al., 2024; Sullivan et al., 2023).

Overall, Cluster 2 presents social connectedness as a complex, context-dependent and it requires careful conceptualization, measurement, and intentional cultivation across higher education.

Cluster 3: Social Connectedness as a Pathway to Well-Being, Engagement, and Persistence

Cluster 3 represented by the blue color consists of 25 studies, and it addresses why social connectedness is important and links it to students' academic and psychological outcomes. Social connectedness is not just a contextual factor, but is a pathway through which individual, relational, and institutional factors have an impact on persistence, engagement, self-efficacy, help-seeking, identity development, and well-being of university students. A large-scale study on university students revealed that social connectedness results in academic persistence, where emotional and academic adjustment act as mediating variables (Mtshweni, 2024b). Social connectedness also functions as a mediating variable between social support and persistence (Mtshweni, 2024a). Social connectedness is positively related to psychological well-being and stress regulation. For example, in preservice teachers, it works as a mediating variable between relational trust and well-being (Bjorklund Jr. et al., 2021). In synchronous distance learning, social connectedness and academic adjustment predict stress, and prior campus experience works as a moderating variable (Jaiswal et al., 2024). During COVID-19, social connectedness acted as a protective factor, but experiences of minority students showed a sharper decline (Barringer et al., 2022).

In STEM and other disciplinary contexts, social connectedness enhances engagement, learning, and identity development. Students who feel connected to their universities report higher engagement and flourishing (Chaffee et al., 2025). In engineering and computer science courses, peer and faculty interactions enhance competence, autonomy, relatedness, and safety (Jessica Belue Buckley et al., 2023; Perlmutter et al., 2023), and satisfaction works as a mediating variable between these interactions and social connectedness towards university (Polmear et al., 2024).

The identity of an individual also influences social connectedness. Racial and ethnic identity can buffer the effects of

microaggressions on African American students at historically White institutions (DeCuir-Gunby et al., 2024). For international students, social connectedness is measured through academic identity and legitimacy (Antonio & Baek, 2021). High social connectedness predicts adaptive behaviors like help-seeking in online STEM environments, while low social connectedness predicts dropouts (Won & Chang, 2024).

Overall, Cluster 3 defines social connectedness as a very important variable to explain how students engage or disengage from university.

Cluster 4: Social Connectedness as a Political, Relational, and Plural Experience

Studies from Cluster 5 were combined with Cluster 4, as Cluster 5 (purple) had 2 studies only and Cluster 4 (yellow) had 34 studies. They view social connectedness as a complex and power-structured phenomenon.

Connectedness can be understood as a relational, political, and plural form which is shaped by institutional norms, power relations, and students' active negotiations. Studies done on UK and Australia explain that students generally develop multiple forms of social connectedness through selective relationships, small acts of reciprocity, and personalized practices, mainly outside the universities (Ajjawi et al., 2023; Rola Ajjawi et al., 2025).

Several studies position connectedness as both personal and political. Using place-belonging and politics of belonging frameworks, they demonstrate that experiences of acceptance are inseparable from broader systems of inclusion and exclusion, including whiteness, class privilege, and normative cultures (Covarrubias, 2023; 2024). Marginalized students face issues in developing a feeling of connectedness. They want to feel included and accepted, but at the same time, they do not want to change who they are just to fit in. Studies define social as autobiographical, relational, cultural, economic, legal, and elective as well (Covarrubias, 2023).

Empirical studies highlight the uneven and multidimensional nature of connectedness. Longitudinal research shows that experiential factors—such as overall educational experiences, transitional support, and connections beyond the classroom—predict connectedness more strongly than fixed identity categories (Crawford et al., 2023).

Disparities nonetheless persist. Lower connectedness is associated with dropout intentions, reduced enjoyment, and first-generation status (Kelly et al., 2024). Discipline- and population-specific studies further show that students may belong socially, academically, both, or neither (Lahdenperä & Nieminen, 2020; Pesonen et al., 2020), while low-SES students often rely on interpersonal support despite ongoing institutional barriers (Walker et al., 2024).

Overall, Cluster 4 explains that social connectedness can be in many different forms and is influenced a lot by political power, which emphasizes the need for critical examination rather than universal maximization.

Discussion

This review helps us know and understand the current research patterns in the field of social connectedness among university students. A large and fragmented literature was synthesized through bibliometric analysis. A science mapping technique, bibliographic

coupling was used to find out the four key clusters that explain the recent research trends on social connectedness among university students.

Cluster 1 conceptualizes social connectedness as a situated and relational process which is shaped by person-environment fit. It is particularly important in high-stakes and marginalizing contexts such as STEM. Social connectedness is very much dependent on institutional climate (Aday et al., 2024). If a student does not identify with the institute, it buffers isolation and distress (Andreadis & Marshall, 2023; Gopalan et al., 2021). Competitive culture and underrepresentation of certain groups of people can hinder the feeling of connectedness (Derricks & Sekaquaptewa, 2021), whereas identity-affirming practices and structured supports enhance persistence (Chen et al., 2020; Clements et al., 2023). In total this cluster explains that social connectedness is dependent on context but is unequally distributed.

Cluster 2 shifts towards how social connectedness is conceptualized, measured, and can be cultivated. It presents social connectedness as a multidimensional concept and it is embedded in academic, social, spatial, and digital contexts (Ahn & Davis, 2019; Allen et al., 2024). Different practices by institution and disciplinary cultures significantly shape students' experiences (Harry et al., 2024; Malm et al., 2020) while digital environments can both mitigate and reproduce inequalities (Brodie & Osowska, 2021; Smith & Watson, 2022). Intervention research showed that it helps in fostering social connectedness. It is also found that increased interaction does not always result in the feeling of connectedness (van Herpen et al., 2019) underscoring the need for conceptual precision and intentional design.

Cluster 3 looks at social connectedness as a central mediating variable which relates student's experiences to persistence and well-being. It mediates relationships between support, motivation, adjustment, and academic outcomes (Mtshweni, 2024a; Mtshweni, 2024b), predicts psychological well-being (Bjorklund Jr. et al., 2021) and enhances engagement and identity development in disciplinary contexts (Chaffee et al., 2025; Polmear et al., 2024). Identity processes further buffer marginalization (Patrick et al., 2023; DeCuir-Gunby et al., 2024). This cluster shows that connectedness works as a pathway by which students engage or disengage.

Cluster 4 extends and defines social connectedness as a political, plural, and power-structured concept. Drawing on politics of belonging frameworks (Covarrubias, 2023; 2024) it shows that students actively negotiate multiple forms of belonging within systems of inclusion and exclusion (Ajjawi et al., 2023). Experiential supports predict connectedness more strongly than fixed identity categories (Crawford et al., 2023) yet structural inequities persist (Kelly et al., 2024). This cluster calls for critical engagement with whose belonging is enabled, constrained, or rendered invisible in higher education.

Taken together, these clusters explain social connectedness not as a single outcome. Social connectedness is a dynamic concept which is influenced by context and individual factors. It is very important for well-being, academic achievement and persistence in university in contemporary higher education.

Implications of the Study

This study has several implications for research and practice.

For early-career researchers, it explains the recent research trends in the areas of social connectedness among university students. Experienced scholars can use the findings to plan collaborations, interdisciplinary work, and studies in underrepresented or international contexts. Practically, the results focused on the importance of inclusive curriculum, mentorship, supportive faculty-student relationships, and relational campus environments in promoting social connectedness. These insights support inclusive, evidence-based research and guide for enhancing social connectedness in higher education.

Limitations of the Study

Even though it is a comprehensive review, it still has a few limitations. First, we included only English-language publications, which may exclude diverse cultural perspectives. We have only searched in one database, which is Scopus, which can result in excluding some important studies which are not indexed in Scopus. Future studies can take into account different databases. We focused mainly on recent trends, but without historical context, the interpretive scope of the review can be narrowed.

Conclusion

This study integrates the fragmented literature on social connectedness among university students. It offers a concise overview of current research trends in the field. A bibliometric analysis was done to understand the recent research in the field. Social connectedness is explained as a dynamic, multidimensional and contextually situated construct which is shaped by individual experiences, institutional environments, and structural inequalities. Four major themes were revealed, which tell about the recent trends in social connectedness among university students. Themes can be summarised as marginalized student experiences, conceptual and methodological clarity, pathways to well-being and academic persistence, and the political and relational dimensions of connectedness. The findings of the study shed light on the role of inclusive instructional approach, mentorship, peer networks, and institutional support in enhancing meaningful connections and engagement, resilience, and psychological well-being. Future research can be done beyond English-language studies, adopt longitudinal designs and evaluate interventions which promote social connectedness across diverse higher education contexts.

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